

Digital research and publication in the perspective of redefining museum digital experience

By

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Working paper

**Lesson presented during the "Re-Defining Museum Digital Experience" Workshop
Organised by the Goethe Institute and the National Museum of Tanzania**

Slides going with this lesson can be downloaded here.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5795604>

Introduction: The Research cycle

a) Plan and design

- Planning research.
- Sourcing grants and funding.
- Applying for funding
- Writing proposal
- RDM service Plan

b) Collect and capture

- Finding data
- Gathering data
- Editing data
- Accessing data
- Searching data
- Developing data
- Storing data
- Clean up data

c) Analyse

- Statistical analysis
- Handling data
- Textual analysis
- Analysing data structure
- Simulation
- Data visualisation
- Data modelling
- Analysing data
- Manipulating data

d) Preservation and publications

- Saving data

- Archiving data
- Organising data
- Preserving data
- Publishing data
- Sharing data
- Publishing research

Part 1 : Digital Research in the age of big data

Online methods to collect data from individuals

The online methods used to gather data directly from individuals include surveys, interviews and focus groups.

Online survey

At the beginning, Internet surveys were often performed via email, where respondents mark their answers into the reply email text. This evolved further and modern email surveys can use Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) elements (e.g. radio buttons, checkboxes) so they are attractive and convenient for short questionnaires where interaction is not required (e.g. no skips).

However, the majority of Internet surveys today do involve some type of interaction. In such a case we typically talk about web surveys, where respondents access and answer the survey questionnaire using a standard web browser on their personal computer or some other device. The responses are subsequently transmitted to a web server, which also provides interactivity (e.g. question depends on a previous answer).

A) Benefits

- The online questionnaire can rely on extensive software for support to allow more complicated answering structures where software will enforce consistency because skip patterns are simply invisible to the respondents when they are exclusively prompted for answers to the individually relevant questions.
- Among the advantages of Internet and email surveys is the quicker turnaround than the traditional postal or face-to-face questionnaire. Large amounts of questionnaires can be completed in a single day thus raising data quality by securing timely data. It is also important that web surveys have a lower cost.
- Primary data are collected for a specific investigation while secondary data are reused by other than the primary investigators. Data are being shared and this also requires sharing the knowledge of the creation of the dataset.
- Internet and online surveys are cheap and fast compared to the offline alternatives. Responses can be automatically checked for consistency and stored directly in a dataset, ready for analysis; indeed, simple analyses, such as descriptive statistics, frequencies and standard cross-tabulations, can be automatically produced. This can largely eliminate the time-consuming, difficult, and costly steps of data cleaning and data input.
- Online surveys are the dominant survey mode for most countries. In an era with high costs for other modes of administration, declining response rates, concerns about registered telephone numbers and increased Internet penetration rates, everyone is doing an online survey. Online surveys are cheap and fast. Software is available for free and surveys can be conducted at virtually no cost. Every action or transaction seems to be followed by a follow-up survey.

- Online surveys are unique in the fact that a researcher never knows how exactly the questionnaire is going to appear on a respondent's screen. In addition, respondents use a range of different devices to complete surveys

Web-based surveys have a number of advantages over traditional pen and paper methods and alternative online survey methods, such as sending questions in the body of an email message, which nevertheless may be useful in some contexts. First, they allow a far greater range of functions to be employed, which can serve to enhance reliability. These include features such as response completeness and format checking, answer piping, skip logic and randomisation. They can also enhance reliability by allowing tighter control over presentation parameters, compared with simple text-based email approaches (the latter may lead to questions arriving misaligned, or in an undesired presentation format). This is an important consideration in designing an IMR survey or questionnaire, given that it has long been recognised by survey researchers that a range of presentation parameters, as well as different response formats, can affect participants' responses and lead to potential biases. Data security is also enhanced compared with email methods, which is an important ethical consideration in most research contexts. Responding to a web-based survey is also relatively straightforward for the participant, as long as they have a web browser and an active Internet connection. Email approaches can require more effort and also allow participants to edit the content in undesirable ways (such as delete or edit questions), and this may cause unanticipated problems (see Hewson, 2003).

B) Issues and challenges

- Recruitment of respondents

- Depending on the availability of a sampling frame, we can speak about list-based and nonlist-based Internet surveys, which can both be probability or non-probability, depending on the (quality) of the sampling frame. The non-list-based Internet surveys where no list of units from the target population is available in advance, are usually based on general invitations where a URL link to a survey is published on some websites or (less commonly) in other media. This clearly leads to self-selection bias, which is out of researchers' control, and consequently to nonprobability samples. A careful invitation strategy can build non-probability samples, which provide effective cost-benefit ratios, i.e. relatively high levels of data quality can be obtained given the costs.
- One of the initial steps in conducting survey research is the decision about target population from which we choose a sample. Here, the differences between probability samples (where we know the positive inclusion probabilities for all units of the target population in advance) and non-probability ones are crucial. Probability samples applied in Internet surveys are highly affected by the problems of non-coverage and sampling frames, particularly in the case of surveying the general population. On the other hand, the non-coverage problem is not that severe in the case of some specific populations (e.g. employees, members, customers). In establishment surveys in particular, it is almost a non-existent problem, as the coverage of organizations (e.g. schools, companies) is already close to complete, at least in developed countries.
- Invitations to Internet surveys are most conveniently distributed using email, but that causes severe problems. There are no email directories of the general population of Internet users that might be used as a sampling frame. This further limits the use of this type of probability Internet survey to specific populations for which such directories exist, for example, members of an organization.
- Online surveys of the general public using email contacts have proved especially difficult to conduct, in part because of the lack of access to adequate sample frames for drawing

probability samples. Furthermore, even within households with Internet access, some adults still lack the skills and/or willingness to respond to questionnaires online.

- Unfortunately, there is no complete list of email addresses for the general population. In general, only institutions that provide email addresses to their clients (students, employees) have the opportunity to survey the complete population via the web.
- Mass mailings with email invitations are cost effective and fast. The downside of using email addresses lies in the frequent change of email addresses, the fact that an email cannot be delivered when there is something misspelled, and spam filters may block the delivery of the email. In addition, many people get an enormous amount of email in their inbox and the invitation might be easily overlooked. When recruiting via email, it is important that the salutation is personal, the content of the invitation is short and to the point, and the authority of the email signature and the profile of the officeholder making the request is high.
- Another way of recruiting respondents online is via social network sites. The reach of each network site differs per country. A combination of new (digital) methods and traditional methods (a so-called mixed-mode approach) probably works best, especially when making multiple contacts .
- Another common problem for many online surveys is that utilizing email messages as the sole means of contacting sample members has been rather ineffective as a means of obtaining acceptable levels of response.
- The special problem of online survey research is that there is no way to construct a sampling frame. Without a sampling frame, almost all Internet surveys rely on self-selected respondents collected into large, pre-constituted panels. This yields cheap, speedy results, but the problems are serious. The core problem is that this process is almost guaranteed to produce biased data.
- However, online surveys are not without downfalls and obtaining proper survey data requires effort and knowledge on the part of the researcher.
- Several forms of nonresponse may occur in Internet surveys. In surveys in general, invited participants can refuse participation altogether (unit nonresponse), terminate participation during the process (break-off or partial response) or answer
- Two aspects of Internet surveys are particularly prominent in such comparisons: response rate and quality of survey answers. We already mentioned that response rate comparisons are usually not favourable for Internet surveys.

- **Ethical issues**

Informed consent

Internet tracking tools can be used to improve the design of a website or to target a specific population. Cookies can collect information about the users' behavior across Internet sessions. They are small amounts of data that are stored on the computer of the web server. Cookies collect information about the user, such as preferences, profile information and searches, and retrieve this information upon the next visit. Participants are often unaware of the amount of information researchers can obtain with online surveys. Respondents are often not informed about the use and the existence of this kind of information, which goes against the principle of informed consent. Informed consent serves to make sure that respondents comprehend what they agree to so they can make an informed and voluntary decision as to whether they want to participate or not. Since there is often no real-life contact between the researcher and the respondent, it is difficult to determine to what extent respondents fully understand the information provided in the informed consent.

Privacy and confidentiality

Although the researcher is responsible for protecting respondents' privacy and ensuring confidentiality, there are ways confidentiality in online surveys typically could be jeopardized. Hackers can get access to personal information, and so-called 'sniffing programs' can keep their eyes on data that are being transmitted.

Online interview

A wide variety of software and services are available to facilitate online communication and, depending on the context of the research, it is possible for researchers to make use of any of these to carry out online interviews.

Asynchronous interviews

Online interviews, conducted in non-real time or asynchronously have been one of the most widely used online methods to date. Software for asynchronous interviews can be divided into two types: email applications and discussion board software and services. Email is particularly appropriate for individual interviews, although the 'copy-to' function of most email applications may allow their use for small group interviews.

Advantages

The main advantages of using email are that it is more likely to be familiar and available to researchers and participants, it does not present problems with the compatibility of different software and systems, and it allows responses to be made privately. Discussion board software and services are more likely to be of use for asynchronous group interviews because they allow multiple participants to view and respond to postings from the researcher or other participants when convenient.

There are a number of advantages to using an asynchronous online interview, not least the relative technological simplicity of email. However, it is important to remember that for some individuals, techno-competence may be inhibited by disabilities such as dyslexia or visual impairment or other, more physical limitations which may make computer use difficult.

A second distinct advantage of the email interview is that interviewees can answer the interview questions entirely at their own convenience. There are no time restrictions and this can be particularly valuable when participants are located in different time zones. Emails can be answered any time of day or night that suits the respondent. The lack of temporal restrictions also enables both the interviewer and interviewee to spend time considering their questions and answers, and perhaps composing, recomposing and editing responses to questions.

The more relaxed timescale of asynchronous approaches can allow greater scope for reflection and checking external sources, which could help produce more reflective, reflexive, detailed and perhaps accurate responses. Nevertheless, some researchers have also reported obtaining rich, high quality data using synchronous methods.

Disadvantages

Although email interviews do allow respondents considerable time to compose, edit and redraft responses to questions, this could be perceived as a disadvantage. A response that has been so well-considered and carefully thought about is likely to produce a 'socially desirable' answer rather than a more spontaneous response which can be generated through synchronous interviews or by more traditional face-to-face interviews.

Some of the advantages of email interviewing can then also represent disadvantages. The frequent time lag between an interviewer posting a question and the interviewee emailing a reply may result in a certain level of spontaneity being lost and this may impact on the richness of the data generated.

the reliance on a text-based interview process can also lead to the researcher becoming 'a victim of his or her own imagination and preconceptions' when interviewing people via email. In a situation where the participants and the researcher cannot see or hear each other and the researcher has to rely solely on the written text to understand the participant, there are concerns that valuable nonverbal data may be lost in the email interview process.

Further issues revolve around the fact that researchers cannot safely ask 'knowledge' questions because respondents can simply check the answers on the Internet.

Finally, there may still be age/generation differences in how comfortable respondents are with computer-mediated interaction via email.

Although there are particular ethical issues that must be considered where an existing board is used, there is likely to be less technical difficulty for the researcher, who simply requires access to a computer with an Internet connection. Creating a discussion board for the interviews, however, involves the use either of a software and hosting service or the installation of software on a server which the researcher has access to. Where a software and hosting service is used, the process is relatively straightforward from a technical perspective.

Synchronous interview

A wide range of software and services are available for synchronous interviews, including online chat facilities, 'instant messaging' and video-based technologies. Many of these services offer facilities for both individual and group interviews and allow for communication via text or via audio and video. Once participants have been successfully recruited, it is relatively straightforward to access a range of free 'instant messaging' services (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger and Gmail Chat), which provide a more secure and appropriate platform for synchronous interviews.

The growth of these services along with the increase in the number, usage and availability of Internet telephony services such as Skype, which allows one-to-one and multi-user audio communication over the Internet, is making their use for audio interviewing increasingly realistic.

Advantages

The key advantage of these services over the free online chat providers is that instant messaging software can be used to set up chats specifically for interviews that can be limited to invited participants only and in which the researcher has a great deal of control over the discussion.

'Real time' online interviews can provide greater spontaneity than online asynchronous interviews, enabling respondents to answer immediately and, in the case of synchronous focus groups, interact with one another. Perhaps the most widely used approach to online synchronous interviews has been facilitation through conferencing software. Relevant software can be downloaded by the participants and the chatroom type environment facilitates the synchronous nature of the interviews.

Unlike asynchronous interviews, where there is time to edit and redraft responses, synchronous interviews can generate more spontaneous answers. This can result in responses being more 'honest' in nature as there is little time to consider the social desirability of the response in the 'fast and furious environment' of the synchronous chat.

On the positive side, however, as with email interviews, there is no need for the researcher to transcribe interviews as transcripts are automatically created.

One-to-one and group communication is possible with many of the services and automatic transcription is frequently available. A number of extra facilities such as file transfer and desktop sharing are often also available. All the services allow real-time text-based messaging and some also offer video conferencing and/or Internet telephony facilities. This makes audio and video

communication possible where the researcher and participants have broadband Internet connections and the necessary equipment (webcams and/or microphones and speakers).

Disadvantages

Some participants may not have the technological competence, familiarity with online communication, software requirements or regular high-speed Internet provision to enable them to participate in a synchronous online interview, which may act as a further disincentive.

A downside of this environment is that the fast-paced nature of the discussion generates interview transcripts which can be difficult to interpret. Contributions can be fragmented and rarely follow a sequential form because the interviewer may post a new question before the respondent has fully replied to the previous question. This results in a transcript that resembles a 'written conversation'.

Although online interviewing may therefore be more time efficient for the researcher (reducing travel times, for example), it may be more time consuming for the participant, and result in the production of less data. Most synchronous interviews employed are based on textual interactions.

In most cases, however, users of one type of instant messaging or Internet telephony software cannot communicate with users of a different type, and the researcher will need to ensure that all participants have the same software installed. It is also likely to be necessary to provide lists of minimum requirements for participants, such as a broadband Internet connection and any required peripherals.

[Online interviews vs face-to-face to interviews](#)

Researchers who have used online synchronous or asynchronous interviews report many differences between online interviews and face-to-face interviews. Some of the challenges related to online interviews are: online recruitment, representativeness, interview conduct and design, respondent identity verification, building rapport and online interaction.

Building rapport and online interview.

Building rapport online, without the usual visual cues used in a face-to-face interview, can be a challenge for the online interviewer. Research conducted face-to-face relies quite heavily on visual cues and such cues can be helpful in building rapport. In the disembodied online interview, both the interviewer and interviewee are relying on the written word as a means of building rapport. The interviewer cannot use body language (facial expression, body posture) or vocal qualities (tone, speed, volume) to interpret what the interviewee is saying.

Interview conduct and design

Conducting the Interview

Conventional interview etiquette, as well as procedural research ethics protocol, suggests that in a face-to-face interview, the interviewer begins by providing a brief introduction to the research project, an explanation of the interview procedure and perhaps a general overview of the questions included in the interview. In most cases, the interviewer would have had prior contact with the interviewee, making initial contact and arranging a suitable venue and interview time. During these interactions, the research project would have been introduced and the research project aims outlined. The virtual interviewer will often lack these early interactions, and opportunities for the building of rapport, gleaned facts concerning profile data and ensuring that the participant feels at ease are possibly missed.

Designing the Interview Script

Before commencing the interview, there is a need to decide how to inform participants about the interview procedure, for example a brief introduction to the aims of the interview, the estimated length of the interview and the types of question. It is also particularly important that a mutually

convenient time to conduct the online interview is arranged, given that interviewees may be in different time zones or have variously timed work commitments. It may also be necessary to remind participants how to contribute to an online discussion.

Online recruitment

A key concern for conducting both onsite and online interviews is the recruitment of an appropriate group of respondents. The Internet provides access to groups of users with tightly defined and narrow interests. However, although participants with narrowly defined interests are potentially easy to locate online, the process of recruitment can be complex. One approach to gaining access to users of specific websites is through contact with website page owners or moderators directly.

Representativeness

Selecting research respondents from the online world also raises issues of representativeness, common to all social science research. However, there are issues associated with the Internet that raise issues of representativeness specific to the type of research, not least access to the Internet itself. The digital divide can therefore still be a very real barrier and some individuals and geographical areas are less Internet connected than others. This raises a serious shortcoming of Internet-based research, often promoted as offering research potential unrestricted by geographical boundaries. Online research methods remain very geographically specific, limiting who we can 'speak' to and whose lives we can engage with. The potential to be involved in a study using online research methods is, therefore, partial, so any grand claims of the utility of such methods for internationalizing research must be treated with some caution.

Respondent identity verification.

In the virtual setting, the interviewer cannot make any assessment of the socio- demographic information which may have an impact on the interview. That said, it is clear that the data collected through online interviewing can be as rich and valuable as that generated during face-to-face interviewing. Indeed, some argue that the quality of responses gained is much the same as responses produced by more traditional methods.

Online focus group

The purpose of a focus group is to enable a researcher to evaluate ideas in a group setting. The environment of a focus group is often thought of as a more natural setting for gathering data, as opposed to a one-on-one interview, and enables researchers to gain additional insights from the dialog and interaction between participants. Online focus groups can be categorized into asynchronous (participants contribute during different times, e.g. emails, forums) or synchronous (participants contribute during the same time, e.g. chat, conference) group interactions.

One unique feature to conducting focus groups online is the ability to do them with participants and moderator at the same time (synchronous) or at different times (asynchronous).

Asynchronous focus group

Advantages

Whether asynchronous methods using bulletin boards, email, social media, or online research communities are truly focus groups has been questioned in the literature, especially when interaction among participants becomes more limited or is non-existent. What makes the asynchronous online focus group different from interviews in these instances of lowgroup interaction is that participants are likely aware of others' contributions; however, empirical research examining the extent to which others' responses are considered by participants in asynchronous techniques is currently absent from the literature.

Asynchronous online focus groups are much more distinctive, especially compared to face-to-face groups. A key feature of this technique is that it allows participants and the moderator 'time to think about answers, to be reflective and introspective, and for views and reactions to mature'. Moderators can more thoroughly review responses and probe more participants.

Synchronous focus group

Advantages

Conducted synchronously, online focus groups more closely approximate the face-to-face medium because everyone is online at the same time in the chosen communication application (e.g. video conference platform, chat room), just as they would be physically for a live focus group. If researchers are conducting some focus groups face-to-face, but must conduct others online due to geographic constraints of participants or researchers, then a synchronous approach can help produce similar data between online and offline collection methods, particularly if webcams or integrated cameras (such as those in cell phones, laptops, and tablets) are used.

This approach is also desirable for researchers seeking to have the live interaction among participants that may reveal important and unanticipated data on the topic.

Synchronous online focus groups overcome a major downside of asynchronous modes: they create better focus on questions throughout the discussion because participants generally avoid talking (if using audiovisual) at the same time.

Disadvantages

On the other hand, it can also lead to only a few people or one person dominating the discussion. It can happen as a result of personalities in the group but also because the limited time leads discussion to move quickly.

Another consideration for the synchronous approach is the time factor. From the researcher's perspective, conducting it synchronously means he/she will have data in the amount of time the focus group lasts (one to two hours). However, from the participants' perspective, this approach may mean it takes more of their time, even if it is only a perceptual assumption rather than what actually happens.

Organizing the synchronous online focus group can be more difficult because everyone has to be available at the same time. Time differences between participants and between participants and researchers can also pose challenges in communicating exactly when it will take place and simply identifying a convenient block of time for all.

When the group is too large, some may feel their contributions are insignificant, demotivating levels of participation and perhaps leading to drop-outs. Having the large group to begin with may leave the researcher with a sufficient number of active participants, but they could be excluding an important segment of their population who simply may not find this method suitable to their communication preferences.

Communication mediums for conducting online focus groups

Text-based facilitation mediums

No transcription is required, likelihood of a participant dominating discussion is reduced, participants can remain anonymous to the group, it accommodates multiple languages, and has a lower technological barrier. Some of these advantages also have disadvantages. Not having to transcribe data is appealing, but researchers will still have to make some decisions about what data to include in analysis or whether to edit.

Although methodological research has not yet noted the use of hashtags in text-based online focus groups, researchers should be prepared to see them as a part of their data, especially among adolescent and young adult participants.

In synchronous focus groups, because participants can be typing responses at the same time, dominant participants cannot 'silence' others through the required turn-taking in communication and the moderator having to move discussion forward due to time constraints. Dominant participants still emerge in a different way by being faster typists. In fact, text-only, synchronous focus groups can be overwhelming for participants who are not accustomed to communicating in this manner.

The asynchronous, online text-only focus group medium produces fewer socially desirable and dishonest responses from participants compared to face-to-face approaches. Even if the topic is not sensitive in nature, participants also tend to feel more open to disagreeing with others, presumably due to the perceptions of anonymity and also because of the lack of additional communicative factors like tone of voice and non-verbal expression. Participant anonymity may pose other challenges though because it 'allows individuals to conceal all or parts of their identity, or in fact allows them to adopt an alternative identity. There is no way to guarantee participants are truly part of the target population.

When researchers require participants whose preferred language is different from their own or participants in a single group with different languages, text-based mediums offer a unique solution to enhance communication.

Finally, in some respects, the technological barrier is lower with text-based facilitation mediums because most people are more equipped for and accustomed to communicating online by typing. Slower connection speeds are amenable to text-based communication and participants do not have to have webcams or microphones.

Video-based focus groups

Many have argued the main limitation to text-based focus groups is the lack of verbal and visual interaction and that is the key advantage to using video-based focus groups.

Video focus groups use people's webcams and online video conferencing applications to conduct them synchronously. They can also be done asynchronously by using platforms that allow researchers to create groups and participants to upload videos, but research or mention of this technique in other literature does not yet exist. Besides potentially enhancing communication among participants and between moderator and participants, video techniques are useful to researchers wanting to gain deeper insights than verbal constructs allow. 'As participants use visual images and metaphors to help describe their identities, experiences, and practices, researchers are able to obtain more detailed narratives. During the transcription process, researchers can also denote tone of voice, facial expressions, and body language to enhance understanding of the data for the analysis phase. Literature discussing the potential of video mediums for conducting focus groups is limited to passing mentions of its potential.

Online focus group vs offline focus group

There are many benefits to conducting focus groups in an online setting: they are relatively inexpensive, provide greater and easier access to a broad range of research participants, and can take less time to collect data. Video communication online via webcams can offer researchers rich data similar to face-to-face focus groups. In addition, the technique allows for more specific framing of research topics and issues by participants, limiting researcher bias.

Much of the seminal literature describing the focus group method was developed with face-to-face communication in mind. Focus group methods are designed to create a group environment in which typically six to eight participants who have some commonality feel comfortable sharing a wide variety of ideas on a specific topic or focus with facilitation by a trained moderator. Most researchers suggest online focus groups use fewer participants than face-to-face. Recommendations vary depending on whether the focus group will be conducted asynchronously (10 to 30 participants) or synchronously (3 to 8 participants). Besides size of the focus groups, the possibilities for the heterogeneity or homogeneity of participants are also more expansive when they are facilitated online. Researchers

seeking data that would be enhanced with heterogeneous groups can have participants from different geographic locations using online methods, which could also add additional variance of other demographic variables.

Although this is true, it is important to bear in mind that online access is not yet universal. As such, a sample will most likely reflect the perspective of a more educated and higher socially located population that has the resources for access either through work or home environments. That said, however, the focus group method still allows for a diversity of participation from within that particular group of people that have access to the technology.

Big data research Methods

One of the features of human life over the last few decades has been its digitisation. This digitisation has made human life inexorably more 'quantifiable' because digital devices leave traces that can be captured. This has led to the creation of large new sources of data on all sorts of aspects of social life. The declining cost of storage and ease of accessibility are driving rapid increases in digital record gathering and storage, reinforcing these trends. The big data approach to the social sciences involves the exploitation of these data sources to answer questions about society.

Broadly speaking, these opportunities can be grouped under three headings.

- First, and most obviously, big data has quantified certain social activities that previously have been very difficult to study systematically.
- Second, and related to this, big data provides the opportunity to conduct large-scale studies of rare events, which conventional random sampling techniques would be unlikely to discover (or discover in sufficient numbers).
- A final advantage is that big data are often cheap and rapid for social scientists to employ.

We can separate these methods into three subheadings, each broadly corresponding to a stage of research: data capture, data interpretation and data analysis.

Requirements

The toolkit necessary to tackle this kind of research encompasses researchers or teams with multiple abilities. These skills can be divided into two sections: ability to write scripts and the need for infrastructural support.

Ability to Script

A fundamental aspect of big data research is the ability to write 'scripts' – small pieces of computer code that can be rapidly brought together to solve bespoke problems. Big data research requires automation that includes instructing the computer to download millions of lines of data, to extract relevant parts of a JSON object into a dataset, to perform automatic content analysis on downloaded text, and more. The standard approach to automation in the social sciences is through the use of pre-existing computer programs with (relatively) easy-to-use graphical user interfaces related to C, R or Python.

Infrastructural Support

The majority of contemporary social science work is done on the personal computers of the researchers involved, either desktop machines provided by universities or commonly a laptop. In many cases, these machines will be sufficient; in some areas, however, this might be more problematic.

Data capture

The sources of big data are many. Any electronic transaction leaves a digital trace. In cashless financial transactions, communication via email, text messages, mobile telephone call records, wikis, games, photo or video sharing sites, or online interactions with official government agencies, many formerly ephemeral aspects of people's lives are digitally captured and stored.

Open data

Many open data stores offer a range of machine-readable download options and some conform to standard metadata schemas; indeed, these have shaped the transparency agenda for some years. However, other open data are published intermittently without dedicated funding to do so and can be less well documented.

Social science data archives, known as domain repositories, are key to data access.

Citizen Science Research and Crowd-Sourced Data : As online data resources for research are so readily available, scientists have begun to exploit the power of new online crowd-sourcing facilities. Sources include social media and images from public interest areas like space exploration.

Despite this heterogeneity of sources, in practice data capture occurs through one of three major techniques:

Data mining

The web offers various forms of data that can be mined, including (hyper)text and multimedia, graphs, actions and interactions, networked data (e.g. social networks), and others. data mining' is the action usually undertaken to study 'big data'; however, one can mine data that are not 'big' or study big data other than by mining it.

Data mining clearly holds vast potential and merit for social science applications. At its best it allows for real-time, remote-sensing, in vivo and non-invasive research, involving a diversity of participants and a massive amount of data.

Data mining research can be divided into three groups based on the different corpora employed: (1) studies that look at mainstream media (such as popular news sites), (2) studies that examine user-generated content (social media, online forums, reader comments, Wikipedia, blogs, etc.), and (3) studies that look at user activity (such as queries to search engines and log files). The first group uses data mining to dramatically increase the volume of the corpus (making the sample closer to the population itself). The second group of studies can consider the structural patterns of communication using network analysis (for example, the network analyses of the Wikipedia discussions among editors, or network analysis of Twitter communication flow). The last group does not look directly at the content but rather at the behavior of users.

Data mining procedures	
Steps	Description
Data cleaning, integration and selection	Removing poor quality data, errors and random noise, handling missing data, mapping data to a single naming convention, combining several sources of data, as needed, and retrieving data from the database.

Data transformation	Data must be converted or encoded into common formats, summarized or aggregated into forms appropriate for mining, and reduced in dimensionality.
Data mining	Applying algorithms to extract data patterns. Some of these patterns may be descriptive, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring and summarizing the dataset using interactive and visual representations, • Clustering – Partitioning the data into groups, e.g. dividing Internet users into groups based on similar usage habits of a particular website or clustering search volume time series based on the strength of their correlations with (1) related news coverage and (2) the academic calendar. • Association rules – Describing relationships between variables • Sequence discovery – Determining sequential patterns in data • Classification – Sorting data items into one of several predefined classes. • Regression – Predicting the value of a continuous variable,
Pattern evaluation	Identifying patterns representing knowledge based on measures of 'unusualness', 'unexpectedness', or 'interestingness'; some of these may be objective and others subjective. the patterns can be considered interesting if (1) they are easy to understand, (2) they are valid on new or test datasets with at least a certain degree of certainty, (3) they are unexpected, (4) they confirm a hypothesis, (5) they are potentially useful or actionable.
Knowledge presentation	Visualizing and representing mined knowledge to the user.

Part 2: Scientific publication at the age of Open Science

Open access to scientific publications is a topic that has been of great interest to a large community of librarians and scientists, particularly in the field of information and documentation sciences, for more than twenty years. The concept of open access emerged in response to the restrictive access to knowledge in scholarly and scientific journals imposed by commercial publishing houses through subscription fees, license fees or pay-per-view fees. Thus, on February 14, 2002, a group of researchers met in Budapest to define the bases of open access. This is the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI).

By "open access" to scientific literature, the Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002)¹ means:

The free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in

¹ Budapest Open Access Initiative 2002

this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited.

There are two basic conditions that must be satisfied before a work can be classified as an open access publication. These conditions are stated in the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities.

- First, the author(s) and right holder(s) of such contributions must grant to all users a free, irrevocable, worldwide, right of access to, and a license to copy, use, distribute, transmit and display the work publicly and to make and distribute derivative works, in any digital medium for any responsible purpose, subject to proper attribution of authorship, as well as the right to make small numbers of printed copies for their personal use.
- Secondly, a complete version of the work and all supplemental materials, including a copy of the permission as stated above, in an appropriate standard electronic format is deposited in at least one online repository that is supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government agency, or other well established organization that seeks to enable open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability, and long-term archiving. The more the work of an author gets cited, the more impact the author is able to make in his/her field of research. With less funding available to libraries and educational institution in the developing world, the benefit of open access cannot be over-emphasized.

It should be noted that, the concept of open access has been subject to various definitions with time, and has had three key moments; before diving in this historical background, let us revisit the basics of Open Access.

Historical background of Open Access

At the end of the 20th century, university librarians around the world found themselves in the middle of a big problem now known as the “serials crisis.”The serials crisis was the result of subscription costs for publications rising much faster than inflation. Hence, they no longer had money for all of the publications they wanted and were forced to make difficult choices between journals.

Early years of Open Access

One early proponent of the publisher-pays model was the physicist [Leó Szilárd](#)(1998)². To help stem the flood of low-quality publications, he jokingly suggested in the 1940s that at the

beginning of his career each [scientist](#) should be issued with 100 vouchers to pay for his papers. Closer to the present, but still ahead of its time, was [common knowledge](#). This was an attempt to share information for the good of all. The modern open access movement traces its history at least back to the 1950s, with the [Letterist International](#) (LI) placing anything in their journal *Potlatch* in the public domain.

An explosion of interest and activity in open access journals has occurred since the 1990s, largely due to the widespread availability of Internet access. It is now possible to publish a scholarly article and *also* make it instantly accessible anywhere in the world where there are computers and Internet connections. The fixed cost of producing the article is separable from the minimal cost of the online distribution.

These new possibilities emerged at a time when the traditional, print-based scholarly journals system was in a crisis. The number of journals and articles produced had been increasing at a steady rate; however the average cost per journal had been rising at a rate far above inflation for decades, and budgets at academic libraries have remained fairly static.

Basics

Open access is a set of principles and a range of practices through which research outputs are distributed online, free of cost or other access barriers.³ Through licensing via an open license (usually a creative common license). With open access defined, barriers to copying or reuse are also reduced or removed by applying an open license for copyright.

The main focus of the open access movement is "[peer reviewed](#) research literature." Historically, this has centered mainly on print-based [academic journals](#). Whereas conventional (non-open access) journals cover publishing costs through [access tolls](#) such as subscriptions, site licenses or [pay-per-view](#) charges, open-access journals are characterized by funding models which do not require the reader to pay to read the journal's contents or they rely on public funding. Open access can be applied to all forms of published research output, including peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed [academic journal](#) articles, [conference papers](#), theses, book chapters, monographs, research and images.

Different open access types are currently commonly described using a colour system. The most commonly recognized names are "green", "gold", however, a number of other models and alternative terms are also used.

❖ Gold OA

In the gold OA model, the publisher makes all articles and related content available for free immediately on the journal's website.

In such publications, articles are licensed for sharing and reuse via creative commons licenses or similar.

❖ **Green OA**

Here self-archiving by authors is permitted. Independently from publication by a publisher, the author also posts the work to a website controlled by the author, the research institution that funded or hosted the work, or to an independent central open repository, where people can download the work without paying.

Green OA is gratis for the author. Some authors may charge a fee license on the publisher authored copyrightable portions of the printed version of the article.

The Budapest Open Access Initiative : phase 1 (2002 - 2012)

The opening statement of the Budapest initiative aptly reflects the objective of the open access movement: An old tradition and a new technology have converged to make, to possible an unprecedented public good. The old tradition is the willingness of scientists and scholars to publish the fruits of their research in scholarly journals without payment, for the sake of inquiry and knowledge. The new technology is the internet. The public good they make possible is the world-wide electronic distribution of the peer-reviewed journal literature and completely free and unrestricted access to it by all scientists, scholars, teachers, students, and other curious minds (2002)⁴. From this initial statement, the first period of OA has been based on a two-track strategy: self-archiving or the green voice and open access journals or the golden voice.

Self-archiving

Researchers need tools and assistance to deposit their peer-reviewed journal articles in open electronic archives, a practice commonly referred to as "self-archiving". When these archives comply with the standards created by the Open Archives initiative, search engines and other tools can treat the different archives as one. Users then do not need to know which archives exist or where they are located to find and use their content.

- Open archives or OA repositories do not perform peer review, but simply make their content available to the world. They may contain unrefereed preprints, refereed postprints, or both.

⁴ Budapest Open Access Initiative

- Open archives or OA repositories can be owned by institutions, such as universities and laboratories, or by disciplines, such as physics and economics.
- Authors can archive their preprints without anyone's permission, and a majority of journals already allow authors to archive their postprints. When archives comply with the Open Archives metadata collection protocol, they are interoperable and users can find their content without knowing which archives exist, where they are located or what they contain. There is now open source software for the creation and maintenance of OAI compliant archives and a worldwide momentum for its use. The costs of an archive are negligible: a little server space and a fraction of a technician's time.

Open access journals

Researchers need the means to launch a new generation of journals committed to open access, and to support existing journals that choose to make the transition to open access. Since journal articles should be disseminated as widely as possible, these new journals will no longer use copyright to restrict access to and use of the material they publish. Instead, they will use copyright and other tools to ensure continued open access to all the articles they publish. As price is a barrier to access, these new journals will not charge subscription or access fees, and will turn to other methods to cover their expenses.

- Open access journals carry out peer review and then make approved content available to the world. Their expenses consist of peer review, manuscript preparation and server space.
- Open access journals pay their bills in the same way as radio and television stations: those with an interest in disseminating the content pay the production costs upfront so that access is free to anyone with the right equipment. Sometimes this means that journals receive a grant from the host university or professional society. Sometimes it means that journals charge a processing fee on accepted articles, to be paid by the author or the author's sponsor (employer, funding body).
- Open access journals that charge a processing fee usually waive it in case of economic difficulties.
- Open access journals that receive institutional funding tend not to charge a processing fee.
- Open access journals may be able to get by with lower subsidies or fees if they have income from other publications, advertising, paid supplements or ancillary services. Some institutions and consortia offer fee reductions. Some OA publishers waive fees for all researchers affiliated with institutions that have purchased an annual

membership. There is plenty of room for creativity in finding ways to pay for the costs of a peer-reviewed OA journal, and we are far from exhausting our ingenuity and imagination.

The Budapest Open Access Initiative: 2nd phase (2012 - 2017 -2022)

In 2012, a second meeting was held to celebrate the 10th anniversary of the BOAI. On this occasion, the initial BOAI declaration was reaffirmed and some recommendations were made. Indeed, for this second phase of open access, the open access strategy was drawn up in the form of recommendations for the next ten years. These recommendations concern institutional policies, open licences, infrastructures and awareness raising.

Institutional policies

These recommendations are of several kinds:

- Every higher education institution should have an open access policy, which will aim to ensure that faculty members will have a peer-reviewed version of their research papers deposited in the institution's open archive.
- Any higher education institution offering postgraduate degrees should have a policy of depositing forthcoming dissertations and theses in the institution's open archive as soon as they are accepted by the institution.
- Any research funding body, whether public or private, should have a policy to ensure that a peer-reviewed version of any forthcoming work which identifies the source of funding is deposited in an appropriate archive and is made open access as soon as practically possible.
- Any university or funding body policy should require deposit in an appropriate open archive between the date of acceptance and the date of publication. Metadata should be deposited as soon as it is available and should be open access as soon as deposited. Full text should be made open access as soon as the archive has permission to release it.
- We discourage the use of journal impact factors as an index of the quality of journals, articles or authors. We encourage the development of alternative metrics for measuring impact and quality that are less simplistic, more reliable and fully open to use and reuse.
- Universities with institutional archives should require the deposit of any research article that can be used in these archives for promotion, tenure, or any form of internal evaluation or review.
- Publishers that do not practice open access should at least allow open access in their publishing contracts.

Open licences

It is recommended that the CC-BY licence, or any equivalent licence, be used as the optimal licence for the publication, distribution, use and re-use of academic work. A creative common license is one of several public copyright licenses that enable the free distribution of an otherwise copyright work. This license is used when an author wants to give other people the right to share, use, and build up a work that the author has created. More so, CC provides author flexibility and protects the people who use or redistribute an author's work from problems of copyright infringement. This is as long as they stick to the conditions that are specified in the license by which the author distributes the work. There exist several types of creative common license. They differ by several combinations that condition the terms of distribution. Below is a table of regularly used licenses.

FIGURE 3: Creative commons logo

Table 2: Creative common license table

N°	LICENSE NAME	ABBREVIATION	ALLOWS COMMERCIAL USE	MEETS THE OPEN DEFINITION
1	"No Rights Reserved	CCO	YES	YES
2	Attribution	BY	YES	YES
3	Attribution –Share Alike	BY-SA	YES	YES
4	Attribution -Non Commercial	BY-NC	NO	NO

5	Attribution- Non Commercial Share Alike	BY-NC-SA	NO	NO
6	Attribution- No Derivatives	BY-ND	YES	NO
7	Attribution -Non Commercial -No Derivatives	BY-NC-ND	NO	NO

Source: Wikipedia

The latest version of creative common license, is the **Version 4.0**, it was releases in November 25, 2013. They are applicable to most jurisdictions, do not need ports and they are subjects of some rights and obligations.

The attribution must be given to the best ability using the information available.

- Include any copyright notices
- Cite the authors name, screen or name, or user ID.
- Cite the work title or name.
- Cite the specific cc license the work is under.
- Mention if the work is a derivative work or adaptation.

Regarding non-commercial licenses, in 2014 Wikimedia Deutschland published a guide to using creative common licenses as wiki pages for translation and as pdf. Besides copyright licenses creative common also offers CCo which is a tool for relinquishing copyright and releasing material into the public domain.

The infrastructure

- Every academic institution should have an open archive, should be part of a consortium of repositories or should arrange to use an external repository for its needs.
- Every researcher who publishes, regardless of his or her field of research and country, including independent researchers, should have the right to deposit in an open archive.
- Open archives should have the capacity to harvest from and deposit in other archives.
- Open archives should make information on downloads, usage and citations available to researchers. This data should be accessible to tools building new metrics. Journal publishers should do the same, whether their publications are open access or not.
- Within reason, universities and funding agencies should help authors pay publication fees for open access journals in an author-pays model. At the same time, they should support or subsidise open access journals that are free to authors.

- When subscription journals allow self-archiving or deposit in open archives, they should describe what they allow in a precise language that can be deciphered by humans, as well as in a machine-readable form in an open standard. At a minimum, the following should be specified: the version of the text that can be deposited, the post-publication period required for archiving, and the types of licence that can be associated with deposited versions.
- Open access repositories should provide tools, already freely available, to convert repositories made in PDF to machine-readable formats such as XML.
- Research institutions, including research funding agencies, should support the development and maintenance of tools, repositories and resources that are essential for the long-term progress and development of open access.
- Academic publishers need an infrastructure for cross-indexing and persistent URLs that is based on open standards, freely available, and capable of handling linking and attribution at any level of granularity, from paragraph to image to statement.

Advocacy

- In the case of open access publications, we should strive to better bring good professional practice to the attention of publishers, editors, reviewers and researchers.
- We should offer open access policy templates to assist universities and funding agencies that may wish to adopt an open access policy.
- We encourage the development of a central source where it will be easy to track the progress of open access through figures and graphs.
- The open access community should coordinate more often. Wherever possible, pro-Open Access organisations and individuals should find ways to coordinate their activities and communications, so as to make better use of their resources, reduce duplication of effort, reinforce the message, and display strong cohesion.
- The global campaign for open access to research articles should work more closely with the global campaigns for open access to books, theses and dissertations, research data, public service data, educational resources and software source code.
- We need to state the following truths about open access more clearly, with more arguments, and to more organisations.

In 2017, there was another meeting where the open access declaration was reaffirmed. In addition, Jean-Claude Guédon, one of the signatories of the first declaration, published a

reflection on where the open access movement is and where it might be heading. Currently, the 20th anniversary of BOAI is being prepared for 14 February 2022.

From Open Access to Open Science : UNESCO recommendation

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science was adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO at its 41st session, in November 2021

Definition of Open Science

Building on the essential principles of academic freedom, research integrity and scientific excellence, open science sets a new paradigm that integrates into the scientific enterprise practices for reproducibility, transparency, sharing and collaboration resulting from the increased opening of scientific contents, tools and processes.

Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

Open scientific knowledge refers to open access to scientific publications, research data, metadata, open educational resources, software, and source code and hardware that are available in the public domain or under copyright and licensed under an open licence that allows access, re-use, repurpose, adaptation and distribution under specific conditions, provided to all actors immediately or as quickly as possible regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status or any other grounds, and free of charge. It also refers to the possibility of opening research methodologies and evaluation processes. Users therefore gain free access to the following:

- (a) **Scientific publications** that include, among others, peer-reviewed journal articles and books, research reports and conference papers. Scientific publications may be disseminated by publishers on open access online publishing platforms and/or deposited and made immediately accessible in open online repositories upon publication, that are supported and maintained by an academic institution, scholarly society, government

agency or other well-established not-for-profit organization devoted to common good that enables open access, unrestricted distribution, interoperability and long-term digital preservation and archiving.

- (b) **Open research data** that include, among others, digital and analogue data, both raw and processed, and the accompanying metadata, as well as numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds, protocols, analysis code and workflows that can be openly used, reused, retained and redistributed by anyone, subject to acknowledgement. Open research data are available in a timely and user-friendly, human- and machine-readable and actionable format, in accordance with principles of good data governance and stewardship, notably the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, supported by regular curation and maintenance.
- (c) **Open educational resources** that include teaching, learning and research materials in any medium – digital or otherwise – that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions, as defined in the 2019 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Educational Resources (OER), in particular those related to the understanding and use of other openly accessible scientific knowledge.
- (d) **Open source software** and source code that generally include software whose source code is made publicly available, in a timely and user-friendly manner, in human- and machine-readable and modifiable format, under an open license that grants others the right to use, access, modify, expand, study, create derivative works and share the software and its source code, design or blueprint. The source code must be included in the software release and made available on openly accessible repositories and the chosen license must allow modifications, derivative works and sharing under equal or compatible open terms and conditions. In the context of open science, when open source code is a component of a research process, enabling reuse and replication generally requires that it be accompanied with open data and open specifications of the environment required to compile and run it.
- (e) **Open hardware** that generally includes the design specifications of a physical object which are licensed in such a way that said object can be studied, modified, created and distributed by anyone, providing as many people as possible with the ability to construct, remix and share their knowledge of hardware design and function. In the case of both open source software and open hardware, a community-driven process for contribution, attribution and governance is required to enable reuse, improve

sustainability and reduce unnecessary duplication of effort. Software code, description of tools, samples of equipment and equipment itself may be freely circulated and adapted provided that this complies with the national legislation in terms of ensuring safe use.

- (f) **Open science infrastructures** refer to shared research infrastructures (virtual or physical, including major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, knowledge-based resources such as collections, journals and open access publication platforms, repositories, archives and scientific data, current research information systems, open bibliometrics and scientometrics systems for assessing and analysing scientific domains, open computational and data manipulation service infrastructures that enable collaborative and multidisciplinary data analysis and digital infrastructures) that are needed to support open science and serve the needs of different communities. Open labs, open science platforms and repositories for publications, research data and source codes, software forges and virtual research environments, and digital research services, in particular those that allow to identify unambiguously scientific objects by persistent unique identifiers, are among the critical components of open science infrastructures, which provide essential open and standardized services to manage and provide access, portability, analysis and federation of data, scientific literature, thematic science priorities or community engagement.

Open Science core values and guiding principles

The core values of open science stem from the rights-based, ethical, epistemological, economic, legal, political, social, multi-stakeholder and technological implications of opening science to society and broadening the principles of openness to the whole cycle of scientific research.

They include the following:

(a) **Quality and integrity**: open science should respect academic freedom and human rights and support high-quality research by bringing together multiple sources of knowledge and making research methods and outputs widely available for rigorous review and scrutiny, and transparent evaluation processes.

(b) **Collective benefit**: as a global public good, open science should belong to humanity in common and benefit humanity as a whole. To this end, scientific knowledge should be openly available and its benefits universally shared. The practice of science should be inclusive, sustainable and equitable, also in opportunities for scientific education and capacity development.

(c) ***Equity and fairness***: open science should play a significant role in ensuring equity among researchers from developed and developing countries, enabling fair and reciprocal sharing of scientific inputs and outputs and equal access to scientific knowledge to both producers and consumers of knowledge regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status, or any other grounds.

(d) ***Diversity and inclusiveness***: open science should embrace a diversity of knowledge, practices, workflows, languages, research outputs and research topics that support the needs and epistemic pluralism of the scientific community as a whole, diverse research communities and scholars, as well as the wider public and knowledge holders beyond the traditional scientific community, including indigenous peoples and local communities, and social actors from different countries and regions, as appropriate.

The following guiding principles for open science provide a framework for enabling conditions and practices within which the above values are upheld, and the ideals of open science are made a reality:

(a) ***Transparency, scrutiny, critique and reproducibility***: increased openness should be promoted in all stages of the scientific endeavour, with the view to reinforcing the strength and rigour of scientific results, enhancing the societal impact of science and increasing the capacity of society as a whole to solve complex interconnected problems. Increased openness leads to increased transparency and trust in scientific information and reinforces the fundamental feature of science as a distinct form of knowledge based on evidence and tested against reality, logic and the scrutiny of scientific peers.

(b) ***Equality of opportunities***: all scientists and other open science actors and stakeholders, regardless of location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstances, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity or migratory status, or any other grounds, have an equal opportunity to access, and contribute to and benefit from open science.

(c) ***Responsibility, respect and accountability***: with greater openness comes greater responsibility for all open science actors, which, together with public accountability, sensitivity to conflicts of interest, vigilance as to possible social and ecological consequences of research activities, intellectual integrity and respect for ethical principles and implications pertaining to research, should form the basis for good governance of open science.

(d) ***Collaboration, participation and inclusion***: collaborations at all levels of the scientific process, beyond the boundaries of geography, language, generations and resources, should become the norm, and collaboration between disciplines should be promoted, together with the

full and effective participation of societal actors and inclusion of knowledge from marginalized communities in solving problems of social importance.

(e) **Flexibility**: due to the diversity of science systems, actors and capacities across the world, as well as the evolving nature of supporting information and communication technologies, there is no one-size-fits-all way of practicing open science. Different pathways of transition to and practice of open science need to be encouraged while upholding the above-mentioned core values and maximizing adherence to the other principles hereby presented.

(f) **Sustainability**: to be as efficient and impactful as possible, open science should build on long-term practices, services, infrastructures and funding models that ensure the equal participation of scientific producers from less privileged institutions and countries. Open science infrastructures should be organized and financed upon an essentially not-for-profit and long-term vision, which enhance open science practices and guarantee permanent and unrestricted access to all, to the largest extent possible.

Advantages of digitally mediated research methods

- Research administration via technology such as mobile phones and laptops can be convenient for participants and for researchers.
- Online recruitment can be quick and relatively cheap.
- The internet can help to reach hard-to-reach, stigmatised and at-risk populations.
- Audio-visual features can help to reach participants with poor literacy.
- Digitally mediated surveys facilitate research of sensitive issues, such as sexual health, by offering privacy during data collection.
- Digitally mediated (private) data submission encourages honest disclosure, enhancing the internal validity of data collected online.
- Automated (digital) randomisation and allocation methods can minimise allocation bias.
- Digital interventions, by their nature, offer standardised content, minimising inconsistencies in delivery of intervention content.

It emerges that online research methods have many advantages such as the reduced cost of conducting a research, the ease of access to data, the multiplicity of data sources, the speed with which results can be produced, the possibility of using artificial intelligence techniques, etc. However, beyond these advantages, what struck me much more is the existence of all these technical, methodological and ethical issues that I did not perceive behind online research methods.

Disadvantages of digitally mediated research methods

- Convenience sampling is used in online research: as the sampling frame is not known it is hard to assess sample representativeness (and, therefore, the generalisability of results).
- Risk of multiple enrolment in online studies can be minimised by using multiple personal identifiers to enhance internal validity of data.
- Researchers should take adequate measures to ensure the confidentiality and security of data collected and stored digitally.
- Study participants should be provided with adequate information about the risks of participating in online research.
- Ensuring exposure to digital interventions as intended can be a challenge. Various digital methods, such as reminders via e-mail, text message, etc., can be used to improve exposure to digital interventions.

The table below summarizes some of these different challenges:

Challenges and issues	Description
Methodological	Online Recruitment of respondents Respondent identity verification Representativeness of respondents and data Low rate of responses Side effects of the online presence of the researcher The quality of the data collected from online sources
Practical and Technical	Lack of technological competences The nature and the volume of data Language issues and other biases in algorithms Access to Internet is not universal
Ethical	Difficulty to get informed consent commercialization and proprietary ownership of online spaces practices of consumption of online material. Privacy and confidentiality. Big data and manipulation Data visualizations are not neutral

Conclusion : Applications of digital research in Museums

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